

**EXPRESSION OF SUBJECTIVE ATTITUDE IN A SCIENTIFIC TEXT
(IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES)**

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Abstract. *This article provides information about scientific text, its types, characteristic features, and artistic text.*

Key words. *Scientific text, technical text, subjectivity, artistic text, speech.*

The main part.

A scientific text is the outcome or outcome of a process for a group of people who are appropriately qualified to perceive and create. To make it as informative as possible, the author should use written language, special products and methods of presenting materials. Often, a scientific text is a work that is published or intended for publication. The texts of the scientific plan receive special elements for oral presentation, for example, a report of a conference or an academic lecture.

The characteristic features of the scientific method are the tone, objective approach and disorganization of information, the structure of the text, terminology, and the special language tool adopted for the presentation of logical materials and among scientists.

A text in scientific style is a standardized scientific system. Importing the basis of the scientific method into the literary language, importing from standard sequences and expressions, using the language of "symbols" and formulas, from zikr and writings. For example, permission to accept in the scientific community: for example, ... it should be noted that the research came to the obtained data ... let's proceed to the analysis ... and the result.

To transfer scientific information to "artificial" language elements:

- 1) graphics, circles, blocks, drawings, drawings are widely used;
- 2) formulas and symbols;
- 3) special terms and lexical features of the scientific method, for example, names of physical quantities, mathematical symbols, etc.

The reference device (footnotes, comments, notes) forms more specific ideas about the topic of speech and serves to implement the quality of scientific speech, such as the accuracy of terms and the verification of sources.

That is, scientific methods, characterized by conformity to the norms of literary language, serve accuracy, precision and laconicism in the expression of research ideas. A monologic form is characteristic for a scientific lecture, the logic of the statement is determined consistently, the conclusions are formalized in the form of a complete and clear expression.

A scientific text is a written product based on scientific knowledge based on theories, concepts or any other subject through specialized technical language. Scientific texts appear as a result of research. They present the development of the research process, its data, tests, results and conclusions in an orderly and systematic manner.

The information presented in the scientific text is the product of methodical and systematic work, as a result of which any event or fact is studied and analyzed on the basis of a number of assumptions, principles and laws. All of the above-mentioned results can be verified, thus ensuring their validity and universality.

Each text of the scientific method has its own logic of construction, which has a specific form that corresponds to the laws of construction. Usually the researcher follows the following scheme:

- Introduction to the essence of the problem, its relevance and renewal;
- Choosing a research topic (in some cases, an object);
- Setting goals, solving certain tasks during performance;
- Review of scientific sources that affect the research topic in any way, description of the theoretical and methodological basis for the work; Basis of terms;
- Theoretical and practical importance of scientific work;
- Content of scientific work;
- Description of the experiment, if it is carried out;
- Research results, conclusions based on its results.

There is a wide variety of scientific texts. Some examples are lectures, articles, theses, monographs, school or didactic manuals, promotional work, and books and journals in general in the health, social, mathematical, physical, chemical, biological sciences.

Scientific text and technical text have some similarities: they use clear and objective technical language that refers to concrete reality. In this sense, they are one and the same.

A scientific text differs from a technical text in that a scientist explains, reveals, and describes the development of a research process to present research findings.

A technical text, while based on science, is oriented toward technological or industrial applications, and consists of explanations and instructions that give practical guidance to the reader's work.

When we talk about literary texts, referring to scientific texts, opinion pieces, etc., we mean the writer's ability to create a story and share it with readers. Fictional texts in all cases, be they real or fictional, proceed from a basic argument and from

there develop on the pages, creating a plot in any case; the subject can be varied and the only limit is the author's imagination.

Before starting to know in depth and detail the characteristics of a literary text, it is important to have an understanding of what a literary text is, so this will be the first thing that will be discussed in more detail.

It is a text that performs an artistic and expressive function (as opposed to non-literary texts that serve to inform or provide insight to the reader). The purpose of these texts is artistic and therefore it is agreed to present a subtle, clean and expressive language that not only communicates but also creates beautiful messages, sonorous phrases or powerful images.

The writer is engaged in giving poetic power to his text, so these are works of a subjective nature and depend on the creation of their author.

Likewise, literary texts offer the reader subjective, free, contemplative, experimental, or contemplative approaches to life, with no other motivation than to evoke these feelings and emotions in their minds. To do this, these artistic texts use a series of expressive resources called tropes, rhetorical figures or literary devices, through which they can use language in a more powerful, dynamic or even rhythmic way.

Features of the literary text

Next, the main features that constitute, share, or are supposed to correspond to different literary texts are presented, which are:

Subjectivity

It is not an objective text that corresponds to reality, but usually addresses the subject from an original and excellent perspective.

Language

In the process of performing the artistic text, he may allow breaking the grammatical rules (something that is very common in poetry), so we can assume that the style of each writer defines him as a literary artist.

REFERENCES

1. Doniyorov X, Yo‘ldoshev B. Adabiy til va badiiy stil. Toshkent: Fan. 1988.
2. Каримов С. Узбек тилининг бадий услуби: Филол. фанлари д-ри дис. ... автореф. –Самарканд: Зарафшон, 1993.
3. Akobirov S. Til va terminologiya. -T., 1968.
4. <https://fayllar.org/v-v-vinokurov-terminning-umum-qollanishdagi-sozdan-farqi-haqid.html?page=4>.